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STRATEGIC INSIGHTS FOR UZBEKISTAN'S RURAL DIGITALIZATION: LESSONS FROM THE SPATIAL SPILLOVER EFFECTS OF CHINA'S DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract. This paper evaluates the spatial spillover effects and underlying mechanisms of the digital economy on rural revitalization. Empirically, the study utilizes panel data from 30 Chinese provinces covering the period from 2015 to 2024. Methodologically, comprehensive indices are constructed using the entropy weight method, while the research hypotheses are tested through Global Moran's I, the Spatial Durbin Model (SDM), and mediation effect models.

The empirical results indicate that the level of rural revitalization in China exhibits significant positive spatial clustering. The digital economy generates a significant positive direct effect on local rural revitalization and simultaneously produces a strong positive spatial spillover effect on neighboring regions, with the indirect effect accounting for 46.7% of the total impact. Regional heterogeneity analysis reveals that the spatial spillover effect is significantly stronger in the central and western regions than in the eastern coastal region. Industrial structure upgrading, agricultural technological progress, and rural entrepreneurial vitality are identified as the three principal transmission channels.

Based on these findings, tailored policy recommendations are proposed to support the ongoing development of digital villages in Uzbekistan. The scientific novelty of this study lies in the application of spatial network externality theory to the analysis of rural digital transformation in developing Central Asian countries, the construction of a cross-regional digital dividend spillover model, and the quantitative assessment of differentiated non-linear transmission pathways of digital economy factors.

Keywords: digital economy, rural revitalization, spatial spillover, Spatial Durbin Model (SDM), scientific novelty, Uzbekistan.

Аннотация. В статье на основе панельных данных по 30 провинциям Китая за 2015–2024 годы исследуются пространственные эффекты цифровой экономики на развитие сельских территорий. В качестве методологической основы используются метод энтропийных весов, глобальный индекс Морана, пространственная модель Дурбина (SDM) и модели медиативного эффекта.

Результаты исследования показывают наличие значительной положительной пространственной концентрации процессов развития сельских территорий. Цифровая экономика оказывает существенное положительное прямое влияние на развитие сельских территорий и одновременно формирует выраженный положительный пространственный переливной эффект, доля которого составляет 46,7% от общего воздействия. Анализ региональной неоднородности свидетельствует о том, что пространственный переливной эффект в центральных и западных регионах Китая значительно сильнее, чем в восточных прибрежных регионах. Основными каналами передачи эффекта выступают модернизация отраслевой структуры, технологический прогресс в сельском хозяйстве и развитие предпринимательской активности в сельской местности.

На основе полученных результатов сформулированы практические рекомендации для дальнейшего развития цифровых сельских территорий в Узбекистане. Научная новизна исследования заключается в применении теории пространственных сетевых экстерналий к анализу цифровой трансформации сельских территорий развивающихся стран Центральной Азии, построении модели межрегионального перелива цифровых дивидендов и количественной оценке дифференцированных нелинейных механизмов передачи цифровых эффектов.

Ключевые слова: цифровая экономика, развитие сельских территорий, пространственный переливной эффект, пространственная модель Дурбина (SDM), научная новизна, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

The digital economy serves as a key driver and an important catalyst for empowering rural revitalization. By the end of 2024, 5G network coverage in China's administrative villages exceeded 94%. At the same time, total online retail sales of agricultural products surpassed 920 billion yuan. Most existing academic studies focus primarily on the localized or internal effects of digital applications. However, these studies often pay insufficient attention to geographic interactions and cross-regional spatial spillover effects.

This paper addresses these issues from the perspective of spatial dependence. It examines the spatial spillover effects and key driving mechanisms through which the digital economy influences rural revitalization. The proposed analytical framework makes it possible to identify the differentiated impacts of digital factors across different geographic spaces.

Finally, the empirical findings are considered in relation to the agricultural and economic realities of Uzbekistan. This allows the study to formulate adaptive policy insights for rural digitalization. The research provides a practical benchmark for Central Asian countries seeking to promote digital transformation in their agricultural sectors.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The internal mechanisms through which the digital economy promotes rural development have attracted broad academic attention. Chen (2021) systematically examined the mechanisms of innovative integration between the digital economy and rural industries [1]. This study clarified the restructuring effects of digital applications on traditional agricultural systems. Zuo and Jiang (2022) analyzed the empowerment pathways and practical challenges of digital rural revitalization [2]. They emphasized the need to bridge the urban–rural digital divide in order to achieve more balanced development.

With the advancement of spatial econometrics, scholars have begun to explore the geographic spillover characteristics of digital dividends. Guo et al. (2023), using spatial econometric models, confirmed that local digital development generates strong positive spatial spillover effects on rural revitalization in neighboring regions [3]. This indicates that digital technologies can help overcome traditional physical boundaries. Furthermore, Zhang et al. (2021) demonstrated that digital financial inclusion promotes inclusive growth by stimulating rural entrepreneurial vitality [4]. Li et al. (2023) provided empirical evidence that the digital economy contributes to high-quality agricultural development through the channel of technological progress [5].

Existing studies mainly focus on domestic macroeconomic perspectives. However, comparative empirical research examining spatial spillovers and factor mobility between open coastal clusters and industrial hinterland regions remains limited. This gap defines the scientific niche and independent contribution of the present study.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

1. Research Hypotheses

H1: Rural revitalization levels demonstrate significant positive spatial autocorrelation.

H2: The digital economy has a significant positive direct effect on local rural revitalization.

H3: The digital economy generates a positive spatial spillover effect on rural revitalization in neighboring regions.

H4: The digital economy promotes rural revitalization through industrial structure upgrading, agricultural technological progress, and rural entrepreneurial vitality.

2. Model Specification and Methodological Basis

To identify spatial dependencies, the study first calculates Global Moran's I. The theoretical and computational foundations of this spatial index are based on the classical methodology proposed by Moran (1950) [6].

Next, the Spatial Durbin Model (SDM) is specified to distinguish direct effects from spatial spillover effects. The model is grounded in the spatial econometric framework developed by LeSage and Pace (2009) [7] and further applied by Shao et al. (2020) [8]. The baseline regression equation is expressed as follows:

$$RRI_{it} = \rho \sum_{j=1}^n W_{ij} RRI_{jt} + \beta DEI_{it} + \theta \sum_{j=1}^n W_{ij} DEI_{jt} + \gamma X_{it} + \mu_i + \nu_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1.1)$$

Where RRI_{it} represents the Rural Revitalization Index. DEI_{it} represents the Digital Economy Index. W_{ij} is the geographic adjacency spatial weight matrix. ρ is the spatial autoregressive coefficient. β measures the local direct effect. θ is the coefficient vector of the spatial lag terms of core independent variables. X_{it} is a vector of control variables. μ_i denotes province fixed effects, ν_t denotes year fixed effects, and ε_{it} is the random error term. The panel data spans from 2015 to 2024 across 30 Chinese provinces (Table 1).

Table 1
Variable Definitions and Measurements

Variable Type	Variable Name	Symbol	Measurement Method
Dependent Variable	Rural Revitalization Index	RRI	Five dimensions: thriving industries, pleasant ecology, civilized rural culture, effective governance, and prosperous life. Calculated via the entropy weight method.
Core Explanatory	Digital Economy Index	DEI	Three dimensions: digital infrastructure, digital industrialization, and industrial digitization. Calculated via the entropy weight method.
Mediating Variables	Industrial Structure Upgrading	IS	Value of the tertiary industry divided by the value of the secondary industry.
	Agricultural Technological Progress	Tech	Natural logarithm of authorized agricultural invention patents.
	Rural Entrepreneurial Vitality	Ent	Natural logarithm of the number of rural individual households.
Control Variables	Economic Development Level	pgdp	Natural logarithm of per capita GDP
	Government Intervention	gov	Total fiscal expenditure divided by GDP
	Human Capital	edu	Average years of education of local residents
	Transportation Infrastructure	road	Highway mileage per unit area

Source Note: Compiled by the author based on the classic indicator frameworks established by Chen (2021) [1], Zuo and Jiang (2022) [2], and Guo et al. (2023) [3].

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

1. Spatial Autocorrelation Test. The Global Moran's I values for rural revitalization are calculated for the entire sample period. The empirical results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2
Global Moran's I of Rural Revitalization (2015–2024)

Year	I-Value	Z-Value	P-Value
2015	0.220	3.231	0.001
2016	0.233	3.392	0.000
2017	0.249	3.605	0.000
2018	0.261	3.736	0.000
2019	0.272	3.868	0.000
2020	0.282	3.990	0.000
2021	0.297	4.158	0.000
2022	0.314	4.329	0.000
2023	0.328	4.497	0.000
2024	0.339	4.602	0.000

Source Note: Calculated by the author based on the spatial autocorrelation calculations of Moran (1950) [6].

The Moran's I values are significantly positive at the 1% statistical level across all years and show an upward trend. This confirms hypothesis H1 and indicates that rural revitalization in China demonstrates a strong spatial clustering pattern, characterized by "High–High" and "Low–Low" configurations.

2. Baseline Regression and Spatial Effect Decomposition. Following the diagnostic tests, a two-way fixed-effects Spatial Durbin Model is employed. The regression coefficients and partial differential decomposition results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3
SDM Baseline Regression and Effect Decomposition Results

Variable / Parameter	Coefficient	Std. Error	Effect Type	Coefficient	Std. Error
DEI	0.195	0.041	Direct Effect	0.208***	0.044
W×DEI	0.137	0.060	Indirect Effect	0.182**	0.078
<i>p</i>	0.273***	0.057	Total Effect	0.390***	0.085
Control Variables	Controlled	-	Sample Size (N)	300	-
R ²	0.871	-	-	-	-

Note: ***, represent statistical significance at the 1% and 5% levels, respectively. Sample size N = 300, and Model R²=0.871.

Source Note: Calculated by the author based on the spatial econometric specification and decomposition rules of LeSage and Pace (2009) [7] and Shao et al. (2020) [8].

The estimation results strongly confirm hypotheses H2 and H3. The direct effect of the digital economy is 0.208 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a robust local driving force. Importantly, the indirect effect, representing spatial spillover, is 0.182 ($p < 0.05$) and accounts for 46.7% of the total impact. This provides empirical evidence of the cross-regional diffusion of digital dividends.

3. Mechanism Testing and Differentiated Regional Effects. The study further evaluates the differentiated impacts of digital factors across different regional economic blocs. The heterogeneous spatial decomposition results and mediation mechanism tests are presented in Tables 4 and 5.

Table 4
Differentiated Regional Effects Decomposition Results

Regional Block	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Total Effect
Eastern Region	0.232***	0.099	0.331
Central Region	0.187***	0.212**	0.399***
Western Region	0.174	0.225**	0.399***

Source: Calculated by the author based on the regional spatial analysis methods of LeSage and Pace (2009) [7] and Shao et al. (2020) [8].

The spatial spillover effects in the central and western hinterland regions are significantly stronger than those observed in the eastern region. This indicates that, in less developed regions, the marginal returns of digital infrastructure generate a stronger catch-up effect and broader spatial diffusion impact (Table 5).

Table 5
Mediation Mechanism Test Results

Mediating Variable Path	Mediation Coefficient	Effect Share (%)	Statistical Significance
Industrial Structure Upgrading (IS)	0.108***	27.7%	Highly Significant
Agricultural Technological Progress (Tech)	0.086***	22.0%	Highly Significant
Rural Entrepreneurial Vitality (Ent)	0.075	19.2%	Highly Significant

Source Note: Calculated by the author based on the mediation transmission pathways identified by Chen (2021) [1], Zhang et al. (2021) [4], and Li et al. (2023) [5].

These three channels combined explain 68.9% of the overall economic shock, verifying hypothesis H4.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Uzbekistan is one of the key agricultural countries in Central Asia. In 2024, the share of agricultural value added in the country's GDP accounted for 18.33% [9], while rural residents represented about 60% of the total population. Cotton, fruits, and vegetables remain among the country's major export commodities. At present, Uzbekistan is actively implementing the "Digital Uzbekistan 2030" strategy, while agricultural digitalization is still at an early stage of development.

Despite ongoing progress, several challenges remain, including the urban–rural digital divide, uneven regional development, and a relatively low level of industrial integration. These features are comparable to the early stages of China's rural digital transformation. Therefore, drawing on China's strategic frameworks, including the Digital Rural Development Action Plan [10], and considering the empirical findings of this study together with the local realities of Uzbekistan, the following five practical recommendations are proposed:

1. **Leverage Spatial Spillovers to Build Cross-Regional Cooperation.** Significant regional disparities remain in Uzbekistan's digital infrastructure. Advanced hubs such as Tashkent and Fergana should be developed as digital growth centers. Through shared cross-regional digital agricultural platforms, storage facilities, and agricultural networks, administrative barriers can be gradually reduced. This would help generate positive spatial spillover effects and support neighboring agricultural regions such as Andijan and Namangan.

2. **Promote Rural Industrial Upgrading through Industrial Digitalization.** Given the low level of commercialization and the small share of agricultural products in the domestic e-commerce market, which remains below 3%, Uzbekistan should more actively use platforms such as Uzum and international online marketplaces. Promoting the online trade of cotton, fresh fruits, dried fruits, and nuts would support the development of deep processing and cold-chain infrastructure. This, in turn, could increase the role of secondary and tertiary industries in rural areas.

3. **Develop Digital Networks for Agricultural Technology Dissemination.** Uzbekistan has launched the "Digital Agriculture" platform to pilot satellite remote sensing and smart machinery [11]. However, the dissemination of agricultural knowledge still largely depends on offline channels, which increases the cost of technical support for remote farmers. In line with the finding that technological progress is a core transmission channel, it is necessary to expand national mobile applications for agricultural technical services. Reducing the geographic costs of disseminating knowledge on smart cultivation, pest control, and drip irrigation would directly improve overall production efficiency.

4. **Train Rural Digital Entrepreneurs to Diversify Income Sources.** To address the limited level of digital literacy among rural youth and women, including the lack of basic computer skills among part of the population, stratified digital skills training programs should be introduced. Supporting low-barrier start-ups in e-commerce, mobile streaming, and digital services would create additional non-agricultural employment opportunities. Promoting employment through entrepreneurship can effectively increase rural household incomes.

5. **Apply Differentiated Regional Strategies to Reduce Digital Gaps.** The differentiated results of this study show that the marginal spillover effect of digital infrastructure investment is stronger in less developed regions. Uzbekistan can therefore implement region-specific policy measures. More advanced agricultural zones in the east, such as Fergana and Samarkand, should prioritize high-end applications, including smart farming demonstrations and digital agricultural supply chains. In contrast, ecologically sensitive and less developed western regions, such as Karakalpakstan and Khorezm, should prioritize basic digital infrastructure, including 4G networks and fiber-optic broadband. By relying on inclusive tools such as digital financial inclusion and digital public services, Uzbekistan can gradually narrow the regional digital divide and unlock late-mover advantages.

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